

1 **Nuclear factors that govern endotoxin tolerance in the myeloid lineage.**

2
3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

7 Tolerized responses to innate immune ligands like LPS are best understood as primed responses
8 informed by an innate immune epigenetic memory. Subsequent transcriptional responses following
9 exposure to LPS in the short or long run are thus tailored to meet cellular needs, executed through
10 titrating availability of nuclear factors that transduce PAMP signals. We measured total transcription
11 in LPS-tolerized or LPS “trained” cells to define and quantitatively characterize changes in expression
12 of nuclear factors associated with LPS tolerance. We describe here a set of nuclear factors, including
13 epigenetic molecules (I e. TDRD7), general transcription factors subunits (i.e. GTF2B), and nuclear
14 receptor Sp110 whose expression was activated or repressed in the LPS-tolerized state. Induction of
15 EZH2, a component of the polycomb repressive complex 2 (PRC2) was a transcriptional feature of
16 LPS tolerance, along with GADD45A/B, suggesting that histone lysine methylation and methylation of
17 the DNA were also important for tolerized responses to gram-negative bacteria.
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28